

IMPLICATION OF FASHION COMMUNICATION IN FASHION INDUSTRY

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Cite This Article: Chaturvedi D, "Implication of Fashion Communication in Fashion Industry", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 5, Issue 1, Page Number 9-10, 2020.

Abstract:

The nature of fashion is to change, fashion is something that is worn by today and is worn out tomorrow. A human being communicated with his or her clothes. Clothes are something that is similar in all human beings; they are worn by all but the same fashion that is similar to all human beings give distinction between all. One Miuccia Prada said "Fashion is instant language, the language of the movement". As the intelligence of a person a person is not visible, but his clothes are. In the recent years, a fashion field has undergone tremendous change; it is because of fashion communication. This is one of the hottest and most exciting avenues to open up in the fashion industry. Fashion communication is the backbone of the whole fashion business. Fashion communication makes it possible for the brands to communicate their products' identity in the market. This is among the newest and most exciting avenues of the fashion and lifestyle industry. It is an enlargement area within Fashion field because of the importance of Digital Media and the online presence of fashion brands and practitioners. Fashion communication has somewhere changed the consumers spending habits; it has also given the fashion industry a huge scope for market expansion. This research paper deals with the fashion communications influence and their impact on new trends and in fashion industry.

Key Words: Communication, Fashion business, Digital media, Expansion.

Introduction:

The nature of fashion is to change, fashion is something that is worn by today and is worn out tomorrow. A human being communicates with his or her clothes. Clothes are something that is similar in all human beings; they are worn by all but with the same fashion, similar to all human beings which gives distinction between all. Fashion communication in broader aspect is every mode of communication that acts as bridge between the fashion world and common people. Fashion Communication is one of the newest and exciting avenues to open up in the fashion and lifestyle industry. In modern trends, the success of a brand is marked and understood largely through its uniqueness in identity. With a multitude of prêt and luxury brands mushrooming in the Indian retail scenario, it has become essential for each one of them to develop a unique brand identity for maximum impact and visibility, in the domain of Fashion and Lifestyle Industry.

Revolution of fashion Communication:

- The first communications of fashion and were sometimes used in royal circles as a way of putting marriageable personages on display. However, with the inception of "fashion" came fashion plates, which can be seen as the true start of modern fashion communications. It was first used in England and France during the late sixteenth century and was a wonderful way to promote fashion in countries throughout Western Europe.
- The French publication *Mercure Galant* was credited as the earliest fashion magazine that was addressed to ladies with the combination of illustrations and magazines. It began the publication in 1672, and historically enough, the *Mercure Galant* was a significant development in the history of journalism because it was considered the first gazette to report on the fashion world.
- The invention of the printing press involved
 - in the mid fifteenth century, a simplified version came for the process of providing fashion information, and one begins to find copies of books on fashion that are dated from the middle of the sixteenth century
 - In the nineteenth century - Friedrich Koenig developed a steam-powered press on which a revolving impression cylinder substituted for the hand press's flat platen, delivering 1,100 sheets per hour and the first used in regular production by the London Times in 1814.
 - In the middle of the nineteenth century- Richard M. Hoe- the rotary printing press was invented in 1833 in the United States by allowed millions of copies of a page to be printed in a single day.
- The fact that the early 1890s was the period during which most of the magazines in the United State began using extensive photographic material is apparently related to the development of improved technology for reproduction of these illustrations.
- The development of the half-tone printing process enabled photographs to be printed on the same page as text without affecting image clarity even when reproduced in large amounts. This new technology marked the birth of the modern fashion magazine aesthetic. Since its inception in the 1880s, fashion

photograph has generated some of the most widely recognizable, provocative, and enduring imagery of our time. For example, *Vogue*,

- The magazine industry is facing its most severe challenge since the 1950s. The ascendancy and triumph of television as America's most popular medium marked this age. In the mid-1950s, network broadcast television achieved "critical mass" in the American marketplace.
- TV Becomes the New Frontier- In the 1980s, fashion journalism invaded a new frontier, TV. Up to this point, fashion was not specifically a topic of discussion on television programmes, but this was all about to change with shows like *Entertainment Tonight* (1981), *Access Hollywood* and *Fashion TV*(1997).
- The key personality in fashion television was the Canadian journalist Jeanne Beker, who launched *Fashion Television* on *Video Hits One* (VH1) in 1985, now a leading style program.
- "Madonna wannabes" emerged after her appearance on *MTV* in 1984; retailers sold Madonna-licensed fashions and accessories. Designer Tommy Hilfiger dispensed his logo-laden sportswear to musicians, who became walking advertisements in music videos; he also collaborated on a fashion show and CD for *MTV*.
- In the 1990s *E!* Networks became a leader in fashion television. By 1998, *E!* offered almost thirty half-hour fashion segments a week including "Fashion Week," "Fashion File," "Video Fashion Weekly," and "Model TV." The network also owns *The Style Network*-a 24-hour channel devoted to fashion, beauty, decorating, and entertaining.
- Social Media, Blogging and Beyond- In 2001 and 2002, Klensch collaborated with *Video fashion News* to produce the hour-long segments, *Trio World Fashion Tour*, for the popular arts channel Trio, which featured top designer collections from the runways of the world's fashion capitals.
- In 2009, bloggers had an enormous impact on fashion, affecting everything from print publishing to how brands market themselves online. There are thousands of style-related blogs on the web these days, and those dedicated to their craft have earned industry recognition.
- The revolution is coming from the people blogging and connecting each other through a variety of social networks (facebook, twitter, MySpace and etc.), they are embracing Barthes belief that "there is no law, whether natural or not, which forbids talking about things".
- The future of fashion magazines. First of all, the websites of the magazines will have to move away from the "blog" format and create an inspiring, tight template for their photo productions or editorial content, a website that has the same feeling of luxury and glamour as flipping through a glossy magazine.

Conclusion:

Fashion communication is an engaging strategy that promotes the product without *pushing* the product. Fashion is a visually based industry, so There are also pre-roll, mid-roll and post-roll fashion advertisements in you tubes, instagrames etc. The advent of the internet and social media, however, allowed for the democratization of fashion. The new influencers in the diffusion of fashion online have removed the gatekeeper of an industry that used to be hard to penetrate. In the future, the digital media will continue to reveal new creative fields with global access, and multimedia features, so we can get a bottom-up perspective on what is fashionable. Overall, digitalization has completely evolved the fashion industry. With the introduction of new technologies and mobile customers can expect to receive a more personalized experience that caters to all their needs and concerns. Digital communication is resulting in changes previously unimagined, and we can only expect this change to rapidly advance. In the future fashion communication in social media outlet can and should take the advantage to promote a company's brand. The more exposure, the better communication. This B2C industry will only continue to evolve as new apps are developed and innovative ways of connecting with consumers are created.

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